

CODE-SWITCHING IN PAKISTANI BEAUTY AND LIFESTYLE YOUTUBE VLOGS: A SOCIOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

In Pakistan, among digital media platforms youtube is famous for sharing creative digital content, especially Vlogs for sharing personal experiences with the world. These experiences involve the unique practices of code-switching and code-mixing between different languages like Urdu, English, Punjabi and other regional languages. This study investigates Urdu-English code-switching in the beauty and lifestyle Vlogs of Pakistani youtube content creators i.e. Nadia Hussain Khan and Fatima Irfan Sheikh to know the communicative and social function of code-switching. The Vlogs are selected randomly and their verbal content is transcribed for further analysis. The study has adopted the theoretical framework of the Interactional Sociolinguistic Model by Gumperz (1982) to examine the communicative and social reasons behind this phenomenon. The results show that the code-switching is not a random practice, but a deliberate approach in such Vlogs where Urdu language is utilized to build cultural identity and emotional connection and English in building technical knowledge, professionalism, and compatibility within the discourse of global beauty. The study concludes, that code-switching is important for Pakistani beauty Vloggers to balance the local and global identity at the same time, contributing to the emerging field of digital sociolinguistics.

INTRODUCTION

Language is a social phenomenon which is representative of cultural, economic and ideological reality of a society. It not only eases the communication process but also reflects the identity, hierarchy in the society and power relationships (Wardhaugh & Fuller, 2021). Pakistan is a multifaceted and culturally diverse country where many languages are used and come into contact on daily basis. The national language of Pakistan "Urdu" acts as a unifying language and English enjoys a prestigious position of being connected to education, modernity, technology and global connectedness. This symbolic capital of English language has made it be perceived as a

gatekeeper language as far as employment and prestige are concerned whereas Urdu and local languages have been perceived as a representative of locality and cultural authenticity (Mansoor, 2004; Mahboob, 2009). Moreover, the other regional languages such as Punjabi, Sindhi, Pashto and Balochi add to the multilingualism of the country. In such dynamic linguistic context, Pakistani speakers naturally utilize different linguistic resources, giving rise to hybrid form of communication that incorporate both traditional and modern aspects.

Consequently, in Pakistan, no language is fixed or uniform but is constantly shaped by social interaction. Code-Switching is a language

phenomenon that is particularly appropriate in multilingual societies such as that of Pakistan. Yao (2011) states that within the same conversation, the process of mixing and switching more than one language is called code-mixing and code-switching. According to the Fishman (1986), it is a person's choice of language in consideration of the suitability of conversational situation, which can be exercised through code-switching and code-mixing. Code-switching is a concept under which there is shift between two or more languages or dialects in one conversation, sentence or discourse event. The speakers can change language to indicate change in the subject matter, change the degree of formality, to express emotions or reach various groups of the audience. According to Wardhaugh (2002), in contrast to switching, code is a neutral term for a language, a variant of any language, and a dialect. This line of inquiry differentiates between the English and Urdu languages. Code-switching is a phenomenon that in a community when two or more languages exist and speakers habitually switch from one language to another language (Hornberger & McKay, 2010). The ability to use two or more languages to communicate with one another and the mixed interaction is referred to as bilingual or multilingual interaction. The purpose of bilingual or multilingual speaker is to make a high quality of communication according to the environment (Prabowo, 2018). Code-switching becomes a communicative and sociolinguistic tool which helps bilingual speakers to bargain meaning to convey feelings, to stress and to provide stylistic effects in computer-mediated communication (Halim & Maros, 2014).

Urdu-English bilingualism has become a significant phenomenon in Pakistan because of the enhanced access to technology and online communication platforms. This has led to the more application of code-switching that is evident in everyday discussions, schools, T.V programs, advertisements and most noticeably in online content production. Youtube has emerged as one of the most important platforms through which people can express themselves and share their lifestyles with the globalized society. In general, youtube Vlogs are a fantastic way to learn and have fun. Vlogs are an enjoyable

way to express yourself online. Video blogs or Vlogs are being used by an increasing number of content creators to share their ideas and experiences. They give their creators the opportunity to record personal experiences, presenting tutorials and communicate with audience in an informal and talkative way. Vlogging being dependent on voluntarily speech, is a good source of investigation of natural language use.

Beauty and lifestyle Vlogs have become very popular in Pakistan alongside other genres of vlogging. The content of these Vlogs is usually makeup tutorial, fashion advice, skincare, fitness, daily life routine, organizational ideas in the home and personal narratives. This content usually uses English terminology related to products, techniques and aesthetics influenced by international beauty standards. Consequently, Pakistani beauty and lifestyle Vloggers often switch codes (between Urdu and English) to educate their fans, explain the products, show their knowledge or keep them relatable. In the sociolinguistic context, the Interactional Sociolinguistic Model by Gumperz (1982) is applied as a theoretical framework to explain the mechanism of code-switching as a contextualization strategy in the digital Vlogs. Every language alternation has its communicative purposes, like the indication of the topic change, the focus on teaching material, feelings, or creating the interest in the audience. Code-switching in beauty and lifestyle Vlogs assists the Vloggers to organize the discourse, keep the audience engaged, and strike a balance between professional competence and the ability to talk to the viewers.

Even though code-switching is widespread in Pakistani digital media, fewer studies have focused on the role of such practices in beauty and lifestyle vlogging, where language choices construct identity and audience engagement. Other multilingual settings such as Indonesia and some other countries have conducted research over code-switching in beauty Vlogs, but such research has not been conducted in Pakistan. To address this gap, the current study examines bilingual behavior of two Pakistani beauty creators Nadia Hussain Khan and Fatima Irfan Sheikh whose makeup Vlogs serve as valuable sources of the language use where the

local culture is combined with global discourse of beauty.

1.1 Research Objectives

- To identify the reasons which motivate Pakistani speakers to switch codes in their Vlogs.
- To know the communicative and social functions of code-switching in a digital context.

1.2 Research Questions

- What are the reasons that motivate Pakistani beauty and lifestyle Vloggers to switch codes in their youtube Vlogs?
- What communicative and social functions are served by code-switching in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle youtube Vlogs?

2. Literature Review

Pakistani YouTube Vlogs offer a precious insight into the modern language usage, especially the process of code-switching that has defined the Pakistani English. Such linguistic practices have been brought about by a long-term contact between Urdu and English due to historical, social, and technological factors. YouTube is a digital avenue where speakers can use multilingual materials to convey thoughts, identity, and interest to audiences. Studying code-switching in Pakistani Vlogs enable researchers to investigate the creativity of linguistic means and changing cultural identities of Pakistani content creators.

Code-switching has been known to be the most notable aspects of multilingual communication. According to Gumperz (1982), the code-switching is not accidental but a kind of contextualization cues that allows speakers to transmit meaning, position, and social relations in the interaction process. This school of thought offers a baseline on the analysis of bilingualism in informal and conversational forms of writing like youtube Vlogs. This study has explored how code-switching in Pakistani youtube Vlogs influence language and culture.

The phenomenon of code-switching is particularly exciting area of research in the study of language diversity. Mehwish (2019) examined the application of code-switching and code-mixing in Pakistani T.V commercials and discovered that it was reported that Urdu-English mixing was very common. For code-switching and code-mixing several Pakistani

commercials were analyzed and found that most of the commercials used at least one time occurrence of code-switching and code-mixing. The study also revealed that Urdu-English were primary languages used in Pakistani T.V commercials except regional language Pashto and Punjabi. The usage of English in Pakistan is increasing due to its high status, connectedness to modernity and to attract consumers that leads to code-switching and code-mixing. Likewise, Ahmed et al. (2015) have examined the code-switching and code-mixing trends in Urdu-speaking EFL students in Punjab, Pakistan. Their research revealed that they had positive attitudes on using the bilingual language which signifies that the code-switching and code-mixing are useful in the understanding and interrelating in the classroom. This study affirms the notion that in Pakistan, bilingualism is accepted socially and is functional as opposed to linguistically deficient.

In a more general sociolinguistic view, the article by KhudaBukhsh et al. (2020) argues about code-switching being a global phenomenon that is being implemented by the growing multilingualism and mobility. Code-switching is most frequently among friends, members of the same family and in the workplace. Also, people can communicate without having specific time and resources for learning a language. The degree of precision increased by the use of multiple languages. This study revealed that code-switching is the best way to assist communication and creates a sense of belonging among the people of multilingual society.

The phenomenon of code-switching and code-mixing is prevalent in Pakistan particularly in social media and print media as according to Hajra and Akram (2025), the process of code-switching on Instagram and TikTok among Pakistani youths is a socially meaningful and systematic phenomenon and not a haphazard linguistic action. They demonstrate through the Interactional Sociolinguistics Model of Gumperz, the influencers switch between Urdu, English and Regional languages as the contextualization cues to transmit identity, stance, emotion and social alignment respectively. The English language is employed to index modernity, confidence and global orientation whereas Urdu and Regional

languages are used to transmit emotional closeness, cultural authenticity and local belonging. The study reaches an inference that Pakistani youths are able to form hybrid identities via the strategic code-switching of with the help of the digital platforms.

Anwar, Malik and Butt (2025) analyzed the linguistic difference between students of both the private and government schools in the District of Gujrat, Pakistan. Investigation reported that the learning of English was more advanced among the students of the privately held schools, and the use of code-switching was more common among them and adherence to English standards of pronunciation and grammar than those studying in the government schools where the students mainly used the Urdu and Punjabi languages with English used only in formal situations. The perceptions towards language were related to social and cultural values: English was related to prestige and professional opportunities, whereas local languages were regarded as the symbols of cultural belonging.

Likewise, in the study, Wali explores the code mixing and code-switching in the Urdu-English newspapers published in Pakistan with an analysis as to the sociocultural reason behind such practice. Through the examination of Urdu print media data, the study concludes that English is commonly employed to convey prestige, convenience and clarity, especially the new and technical ideas that do not have an equivalent in Urdu. The instances of code mixing have been found on different levels of language and it usually involves the hybridization of both the English language with Urdu Grammar and this is considered a mixed language called Urduish. The socially constructed aspect of the practice serves in a way of a modernity, education and exposure to the world, particularly in fashion and beauty areas. In general, the study has indicated code-mixing as an outcome of globalization effect on language and identity in Pakistan.

Nisa et.al (2021) have examined the code-switching between EFL learners during speaking tests among students and focusing on its kinds and motives. Based on Poplack's model, the most common switching was intra-sentential switching, which was found in the study (1980)

the most common type (69.49%), next in line was inter-sentence switching (27.12%), and lastly came tag switching (3.39%). By using the framework by Hoffman (1991) the information found that students were using the code-switching as a means of communicating and socializing like, clearing up meaning, emphasizing points, repetition as a way of getting things straight, group identity expression. The study shows that the process of code-switching serves as a communicative facility instead of linguistic weakness.

To unravel the causes of code-switching and code-mixing among bilingual youth in multicultural Multan, Hussain et.al (2025) investigated the motivational factors and sociocultural roles of code-switching and code-mixing in identity development of bilingual youth. The study employed mixed-method design and established that such practices play important communicative and social functions that include emotional expression, identity assertion, social acceptance, ease of communication and cultural and religious identities negotiation. The results also suggest that bilinguals can use mixed codes in a strategically planned way to form hybridized identities and adjust to the offline and online environment, even though they have to deal with such obstacles as linguistic stigma in formal spaces. In general, the study identifies code-switching and code-mixing as deliberate sociolinguistic assets, and provides pertinent information about the sociolinguistic analysis of similar act in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle youtube Vlogs.

Even though a number of studies have discussed the concept of code-switching and code-mixing in Pakistan, a majority of the research has been done in the context of newspapers, ads, classes, socialization, and even social networks like Instagram, TikTok, and Facebook. Although particular literature on the topic of code-switching in beauty and lifestyle Vlogs exists internationally, the previous research does not cover these practices with respect to the Pakistani context of youtube. Specifically, no research has conducted a thorough study on the motivation of code-switching or its communicative and social roles in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle Vlogs. This research

addresses this gap by focusing on the communicative and social functions of code-switching in Pakistani beauty and lifestyles youtube Vlogs.

3. Methodology

The present study has adopted qualitative research design (Creswell, 2014) to examine the practice of code-switching in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle youtube Vlogs. The qualitative methodology is suitable because it enables to conduct a detailed study of the language use in a natural digital environment and to concentrate on the way meaning is created with bilingual practices. The research does not focus only on the linguistic characteristics of code-switching but on the social and communicative roles that the practices play in the online context. The study discusses the discourse of Vlogs concerning audience interactivity, identity construction and the wider sociocultural context within which the Vlogs are created and viewed.

3.1 Data Collection

The data is collected on the basis of selected makeup and lifestyle Vlogs of two popular Pakistani youtubers, Nadia Hussain Khan and Fatima Irfan Sheikh. The channels are chosen strategically because of their popularity, regular use of Urdu-English code-switching in their content that dealt with beauty, makeup, skincare and lifestyle. The Vlogs are selected that clearly show the examples of code-switching but the Vlogs with low-quality audio and little verbal contact were excluded. The verbal data gathered in the selected Vlogs were transcribed so that the code-switching could be identified easily. The data collection procedure involved repeatedly watching the Vlogs and close monitoring of the verbal discourse within the situational context. The analysis is directed by the Interactional Sociolinguistic Model by John Gumperz (1982) which focuses on how the contextualization cues and social meaning contribute to a conversational interaction. This framework is of great use to digital discourse where the examples of code-switching taken from Vlogs are analyzed to determine the communicative and social roles that they are concerned with, like stressing the point, establishing unity with the audience,

persuasion, social alignment or discourse management.

4. Data Analysis

Code-switching denotes the practice of using two or more languages in one interaction, sentence or discussion. The process of code-switching is a typical communication activity in multilingual cultures like in Pakistan, especially among the youth as digital content creators. In spite of the status of English as one of the official languages in Pakistan, Urdu is the national language and it is very common in the normal interactions. Beauty and lifestyle vlogging is a non-formal and strong performative digital environment in which identity formation and interaction are primary. Under these circumstances, there is no random code-switching, it is an instrument of meaning-making. Consequently, beauty and lifestyle Vloggers of Pakistani origin often switch between English and Urdu when producing digital media on the internet. In the digital discourse like the youtube Vlogs, code-switching is strategically used to facilitate better understanding, and keep the interest of the audience. Pakistani beauty Vloggers especially those who are targeting international audiences often switch and mix Urdu and English in order to effectively communicate in a multilingual and transnational environment.

In order to examine these linguistic changes, the current study uses the Interactional Sociolinguistic Model set forth by Gumperz (1982), according to which code-switching is considered an instance of a contextualization cue, i.e. a marker that enables the listeners to make sense of meaning, purpose, tone, and social status. Gumperz distinguishes between situational code-switching (where the change happens because of a situation, topic or participants), and metaphorical code-switching (where the language shift does not involve a change in situation, but only symbolically or socially).

The use of code-switching (CS) is the common practice of Nadia Hussain, a famous Pakistani model and beauty expert. The language use in her Vlogs is AN indicative of her linguistic competence as well as her understanding of her multilateral audience, who may be both local Urdu-speaking and international English-

speaking audiences. The Vlogs of beauty, makeup, and lifestyle by Nadia Hussain is a powerful example of how code-switching can be considered significant sociolinguistic activity in Pakistani digital media. Being a well-liked makeup influencer, she has always used both Urdu and English to provide tutorials, product explanations, and lifestyle content, which is an accurate reflection of the bilingual nature of her audience. Her wordings are not arbitrary, but carefully applied to display cultural friendliness, technical competence and professional power.

Some examples of code-switching from her Vlogs are here:

1. *“Assalamoalaikum main hun Nadia Hussain, Welcome to my youtube channel”*

This statement is an indication of metaphorical code-switching and not situational switching because the participants, the platform and the communicative environment remain the same. The Urdu-Islamic salutation, “Assalamoalaikum”, and the speaker identifying herself, “main hun Nadia Hussain”, this creates a cultural authenticity, warmth and religious identity with the Pakistani audience. The instant shift into English, “Welcome to my youtube channel”, is a contextualization cue which can be interpreted as professionalism, global orientation, and the digital media norms. Pakistani identity and closeness to Pakistanis viewers are indicated by the greeting, “Assalamoalaikum” and self-introduction in Urdu, which personalize the viewers. Objectivization is performed through the use of the switch to English “Welcome to my youtube channel” and makes the vlog look like a professional, global digital item.

Gumperz (1982) argues that such kind of code-switching does not indicate a situation change, but rather carries on multiple layers of social meanings and it acts as a contextualization cue which makes the interaction seem to be inclusive and globally oriented. This change is due to the intention of delivering the message to the overseas audiences, though its role is to capture the attention of the masses with diverse language interests.

The use of Urdu language signifies the cultural proximity and belonging whereas, the use of English language signifies the modernity and

involvement in the global beauty discourse. The bilingual opening, in its turn, creates a hybrid identity, which is on one hand is tied to the local culture and on the other hand is oriented towards the international digital platforms, which enables Nadia Hussain to speak to the local and international audiences at the same time.

2. *“Thora sa gap aa gya tha meri videos ki recording mein but anyway I am back and I am back with lots of makeup tips and techniques and tricks”.*

The switching between the Urdu and English language is metaphorical code-switching in this sentence. The Urdu sentence “Thora sa gap aa gya tha meri videos ki recording mein” gives a sense of informality and personal openness to tell the audiences the personal reason for her absence and creates a conversational style of text that is well-received by local audience. The transition to English “but anyway I am back and I am back with lots of makeup tips and techniques and tricks” is one of the transitions to the professional reassurance and the content promotion. This intra-sentential code-switching put emphasis on the informational and professional nature of the vlog. The switch highlights both professionalism and content value (makeup tips and techniques and tricks) which is a term that is prominent in the beauty talk across the world. The role of this switch is to appeal to the masses, especially those who are conversant with the international beauty lingo. In the case of Gumperz, this switch puts in perspective, the role of a speaker as a professional makeup artist and fulfills the role of credibility and engagement of the audience. The switch enables Nadia Hussain to be emotionally approachable and at the same time professionally credible in the same communicative frame.

3. *“And I’m back with another tutorial aur aj ka topic bohat hi interesting hai and that is placement, the correct placement of contour and blush-on”.*

This statement is a metaphorical code-switching because the change of language is intentional and not a reaction to a change of situation. The English speech “And I’m back with another tutorial” introduces the content in a refined and professional way, which is characteristic of

youtube beauty discourse. Nadia switches between English and Urdu to describe the subject matter and the technical side of the subject. Gumperz says, code-switching is a cue of contextualization, in other words, it is what helps the listeners understand that various sections of the message are meant in different ways. Here, Nadia speaks as a friend in a culturally recognizable manner, by introducing the topic in Urdu, which serves to form intimacy and connection with her local audience, she uses Urdu to introduce the topic in a friendly and culturally familiar way, namely, by saying, “aur aj ka topic bohat hi interesting hai”. Then she changes to English technical explanation “the placement, the right placement of contour and blush-on” since English is the dominant language in the discourse of beauty and cosmetics around the world.

Thus, switching to English triggers the use of technical terminology that is identified with international makeup usage. Gumperz (1982) argues that this switching is a contextualization cue which divides evaluative commentary (Urdu) and instructional authority (English). This alternation also enables Nadia Hussain to convey the sense of relatability and experience, building an identity that is friendly, experienced, and internationally knowledgeable at the same time.

4. *“Dot size primer jo hai wo main laga rahi hun only on the parts jahan py mery pores thory bht wazeh hain, which is on the nose, cheeks and little bit on forehead and around the mouth”.*

Here is an illustration of metaphorical as well as intra-sentential code-switching in which Urdu and English are closely interlaced in single sentence. The Urdu forms like “jo hai wo main laga rahi hun” and “jahan py mery pores thory bht wazeh hain” offer procedural clarification in a culturally comprehensible style. In this instructional utterance, the English terms used, such as “dot size primer which is, on the nose, cheeks...” have brought in technical terms of make-up. The change here is in order to guarantee international intelligibility because the beauty related terminology is internationally standardized in the English language.

Gumperz (1982) found that the English insertions perform the role of contextualization

cues that mark the precision of technical and expert knowledge and Urdu use the clarity of instruction and comfort of the audience. The approach of bilingualism shows the way beauty influencers maintain localized communication and still use the English-dominant cosmetic terms, which supports the fact that Nadia Hussain is a proficient professional and a culturally oriented instructor. In order to clear instructions, retain professional authority and to make the audience understand the instructions in the maximum possible way is the main reason of code-switching.

5. *“Main bohat hi aik quick Eid makeup tutorial karun gi jis mein main minimal qism ki cheezein istemal karun gi to let’s get down to it immediately”.*

This statement is an apparent example of the metaphorical code-switching. Urdu used by the speaker serves to contextualize the cultural and religious background, namely, “Eid makeup tutorial”, “minimal qism ki cheezein istemal karun gi” which makes the content fitting the Pakistani traditions and expectations of the audience. Switching to English like “let’s get down to it immediately”, is an indicator of action and efficiency. Here, Nadia changes language to English to make a transition between explanation and action. Urdu is concerned with establishing the cultural context (Eid) which builds personalization and emotional aspect, whereas English is concerned with action and immediacy. In accordance with Gumperz (1982), such a shift is a contextualization cue and shows that there is a shift in mode of interaction but not context. Urdu creates cultural salience and emotional impact, whereas English creates procedure momentum and corresponds to the global style of youtube presentation. Such bilingual alternation allows Nadia Hussain to skillfully combine the religious-cultural identity with new digital professionalism.

Fatima Irfan Sheikh is a popular Pakistani beauty and lifestyle you-tuber, and the content of her blog videos mostly consists of reviews of make-up, skin care, fashion tips, and recommendations of products at affordable prices. Her Vlogs are conversational and have a similarity to daily verbal communication, which permits unrestricted and frequent cases of Urdu-

English code-switching. Since she is a Pakistani influencer with a largely local following, she satisfies the needs and demands of the native language, Urdu, and employs English as a convenient means to add technical vocabulary to her speech, stressing the importance of professionalism, and meet the requirements of the global discourse of beauty. The subsequent examples are the illustration of how code-switching is a contextualization cue in accordance with the theory of Gumperz (1982).

1. *“Aj mn nikli hun for finding out really really cool bridal kits for you all under the budget of 10 to 15 thousands”.*

In this statement, Fatima Irfan Sheikh starts in Urdu and then changes into English to explain the reason behind her outing. The given example is a kind of metaphoric code-switching, because the switch is not based on a change in circumstances but communicative focus. The English terms like “for finding out”, “really really cool bridal kits” and “under the budget” are also used as contextualization signals that indicate the manifestation of professionalism, trend-consciousness and correspondence to the commercial terminology of beauty marketing. Gumperz (1982) states that this metaphorical switching is employed to indicate social meanings. In this case, English could be linked with the beauty industry in the world, trends on the market, and influencer culture, whereas Urdu can be regarded as culturally familiar. The alternation assists Fatima to draw herself as both culturally rooted and digitally up to date, thus, her material being attractive to a bilingual audience.

2. *“Agr ap yh online lena chahein, you can obviously use my code, jo k mention huwa hai, and you can save money”.*

This statement has a series of switches between Urdu and English language, which is intra-sentential and metaphorical code-switching. This is an illustration of strategic code-switching in a commercial context. The speaker also switches between Urdu and English to provide the information concerning online shopping and promo or offer codes. The words of the English language, “you can obviously use my code” and “you can save money”, serve as

contextualizing signals related to online shopping and influencer marketing. In the context of the framework of Gumperz, this switch acts as a contextualization cue of persuasion and professionalism. English is used to focus on credibility, authority and understanding of the online shopping customs whereas Urdu is used to remain warm and accessible. This code-switching is used as an address to the audience and the speaker becomes an honest advisor in the digital marketplace. The changing of codes assists Fatima in conveying the promotional material and maintaining the conversational and relatable style.

3. *“I am so scared of wearing white pants q k wesey hi khrab ho jati hain”.*

The switch signifies metaphorical code-switching because of lack of a situational change. The emotional position is introduced by English (I am so scared), and the reason is explained in the culturally expressive way in Urdu. In this quote, the speaker uses English at the beginning of the utterance in order to deliver an emotional response and then switches to Urdu to justify why. Gumperz (1982) holds the view that such switching entails personalization and emotional identification. Here English is applied to dramatize fear and relatability, whereas Urdu expresses daily based reasoning in a common cultural experience. The change adds more intimacy, thus making the content more interesting to the viewers.

4. *“yeh to main bohat confidently keh sakti hun k I am a good mascara judge at least”.*

In this sentence, Fatima alternates between Urdu and English when she makes a self-praise statement. It is a pure instance of metaphorical code-switching when the English sentence is used as the indicator of confidence and proficiency. In this example, metaphorical code-switching is used to exert authority. The statement of qualification, “I am a good mascara judge”, is stated in English, rest of the discussion is in Urdu. In his view, Gumperz sees English as a reference of contextualization of authority and objectivity. English can also be regarded as a source of expertise, knowledge about the products, and international standards in the beauty discourse. Switching to English makes

Fatima even more credible, as a beauty influencer, without losing the intimacy in conversation by switching to Urdu.

5. "Now I want to discuss most important thing jo abi apna muh dhoty huwy mny realize ki thi".

This example gives evidence of metaphorical code-switching used for topic framing. In this case, English is spoken to indicate the change of the topic and emphasize on the significance of the following discussion. The discourse-organizing cue is seen in phrase "Now I want to discuss most important thing". The subject matter is introduced in an organized and thoughtful way with the use of English, which is an indication of significance and concentration. The personal context and immediacy are brought in by the switch to Urdu. Gumperz (1982) says that these switches are useful in organizing interaction and directing the expectations of listeners. Urdu then proceeds to unfold a personal realization, which confirms the emotional sincerity and cultural foundation.

5. Findings and Discussion

This study examines the application of Urdu-English code-switching in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle youtube Vlogs, centering on the content of Nadia Hussain and Fatima Irfan Sheikh. The results indicate that code-switching is a systematic and organized communicative process and not a chance linguistic event. The makeup Vloggers like Nadia Hussain and Fatima Irfan Sheikh, always mix Urdu, the national language of Pakistan, with English to strike a balance between cultural and global appeal. Urdu is the key language of emotionality, cultural intimacy, and everyday communication whereas English is used to convey technical knowledge of beauty, structuring and standardizing discourse and aligning information with the global trends of beauty and lifestyles. Such bilingualism is a representative of the dual language reality of Pakistani digital space where the local identity and global communication coexist.

Based on the Interactional Sociolinguistic Model introduced by Gumperz (1982), the analysis proves that the process of code-switching in beauty and lifestyle Vlogs is a contextualization cue that indicates expertise, change of topic, emotional tone, attention to the audience, and professionalism in digital space.

The English language is often applied in instructional parts, product descriptions, advertisements, and changes of the topic, which ranks English vocabulary as a sign of professionalism, authority, and digital competence. Urdu, in its turn, is employed to share personal experience, feelings, and cultural allusions, which help to build intimacy and trust with the audience. This metaphorical code-switching helps the Vloggers to easily switch between the role of a friendly conversational speaker and a knowledgeable beauty expert in the same conversation. The findings also show that code-switching has various communicative and social purposes in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle youtube Vlogs. The main reason behind the code-switching is to express messages to a larger and more diverse audience such as international viewers because English works as a global lingua franca in digital media. Vloggers use English as well as Urdu, which means that their content is not limited by national borders. The other notable impact of the practice is the attraction and engagement of the audience since the bilingual discourse seems innovative, trendy, and understandable to the digitally conscious audience. Code-switching is also helpful in clarifying information, particularly describing how the makeup is applied, skincare tips, and information about the products, where the English language terms are generally accepted and desired.

On the whole, the analysis demonstrates that code-switching in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle youtube videos is a socially predetermined practice of discourse that transcends the linguistic need. It is used as the source of building a modern but culture-based identity, presenting education, sophistication, and professional authority, and enhancing relationships between influencers and the audience. The mixture of Urdu and English languages is a sign of the changing sociolinguistic situation in Pakistan whereby digital platforms allow the content creators to bargain multilingual identities and engage in cross-cultural flows across the globe. In this way, code-switching can be seen as an important technique that helps Pakistani beauty Vloggers attract the audience, be effective in cross-linguistic

communication as well as position themselves in both local, as well as global online communities.

6. Conclusion

The study has used the Interactional Sociolinguistic Model by Gumperz (1982) to investigate the code-switching in Pakistani beauty and lifestyle YouTube Vlogs. The results indicate that the phenomenon of code-switching is not a random linguistic change but a systematic and socially significant phenomenon. Cultural identity, emotional proximity and conversational engagement are usually expressed through Urdu language, whereas technical knowledge, professionalism and identification with the global beauty discourse are conveyed through English language. The analysis shows that Vloggers alternate the codes to structure discourse, establish expertise, publicize products and to keep the audience entertained. Such linguistic switching is the reality of the Pakistan as multilingual country and it helps the creators of different content to reconcile between local cultural values and new digital identities. In general, the code-switching in the beauty and lifestyle Vlogs can be viewed as an effective approach to communication that has been used to create identity and interaction within the digital environment. The study contributes to the field of digital sociolinguistics as it emphasizes youtube as an important source of analyzing language practices in modern Pakistan.

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